

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING A STUDENT'S PEDAGOGICAL ABILITY

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Аннотация: В представлениях о возможностях проявления и продвижения талантов в статье рассматриваются индивидуальные усилия человека как основной источник развития талантов, а ответственность за развитие талантов на национальном уровне лежит на талантливых людях, отмечается, что за них необходимо платить. внимание к этим аспектам в развитии таланта ученика.

Ключевые слова: талант, идея, личность, человечность, ответственность.

Abstract: In the ideas about talent manifestation and promotion opportunities, the article considers individual human efforts as the main source of talent development, and the responsibility for talent development at the national level lies with talented people. it is noted that it is necessary to pay attention to these aspects in the development of the student's talent.

Key words: talent, idea, personality, humanity, responsibility

Pedagogical excellence is, first of all, a high level of professional activity, a set of personal characteristics and qualities capable of creatively overcoming various pedagogical situations in the educational process.

There are several components of pedagogical skills.

First of all, of course, this is a humanitarian direction, according to which a person is considered the highest value, his interests and needs are taken into account. There are only humanistic relations and communication styles between people.

Secondly, a high level of culture (both general and pedagogical).

Thirdly, the teacher's professional qualities are love for children, responsibility, morality, patriotism, hard work, stress tolerance.

Love for children must be combined with demand, which educates students, prevents negative actions and encourages positive ones. But there should be a sense of proportionality in the requirements so that schoolchildren do not have uncertainty about their abilities or knowledge.

Fourth, professional knowledge system, communication skills, research, diagnosis, organizational, design and skills.

Fifth, the teacher's creativity is manifested in the ability to creatively approach all problems and educational tasks in the educational process.

In addition to the components, the levels of pedagogical skills can also be distinguished:

Level 1 - reproductive (simulation of activity). It includes the use of work samples developed by other teachers, methodologists or scientists in their work.

Stage 2 is constructive. It combines personal teaching experience and recommendations of other teachers, methodologists and scientists.

Stage 3 is creative. Based on personal accumulated experience in the process of experimental work, the teacher creates a personal (authorship) methodology of education and training.

If we talk about the concept of pedagogical skill, then the term "pedagogical technique" should be mentioned.

Thus, pedagogical technology is a set of tools, methods, skills and characteristics of the teacher's behavior, the creative nature of educational activities and the most effective conditions for motivating students, ensuring the development of the child as a person.

These include:

- self-regulation - the ability to control one's emotions and feelings; the ability to walk, sit, stand. The teacher's skills are also reflected in diction, voice, and facial expressions. A very loud voice, sometimes turning into a scream, has a bad effect on the student's nervous system. The teacher's speech should be open, expressive and logically consistent.

Under the influence of specially organized training of students for teaching activities, as an auxiliary and at the same time structural element of professional competence and professional skills of pedagogical potential, based on such components of pedagogical potential as inclination, readiness and inclusion. is developing consistently.

Conducting the preliminary experiment made it possible to determine that the method of developing the pedagogical potential of students based on the use of elements of

developmental educational technologies at the University of Physical Education will be most effective if the following are used:

Step-by-step formation of components of pedagogical potential of physical education university students.

Directing students to self-knowledge and acquisition of knowledge in the process of independent search for solutions to pedagogical problems.

Pay attention to the formation of internal motivation of students

Elements of mutual evaluation and mutual learning

During the main experiment, the features of the methodology for developing the pedagogical potential of students based on the use of elements of developmental educational technologies were highlighted.

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